

Decentralized Management of IoT Platform Federations and Data Marketplaces

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Abstract. The Internet of Things (IoT) paradigm has been rapidly adopted in a plethora of application domains, promoting the development of a variety of smart services relying on data from different sources. As a consequence, Sensing-as-a-Service is also gaining popularity, enabling IoT data providers and consumers to share, exchange and trade IoT data. In such a data-driven ecosystem, data marketplaces play a pivotal role, which besides the need for interoperable solutions, necessitates also sophisticated market mechanisms that ensure trusted and secure data exchange. In this paper, we present the IoTfeds solution which offers a complete open source interoperability framework combined with blockchain technologies, and thus provides a decentralized federation management and marketplace platform. The IoTfeds platform enables trustworthy and secure transactions allowing the creation and monetization of composite IoT data services offered by multiple federated data providers.

Keywords: federated marketplaces · IoT data market · blockchain

1 Introduction

Data markets have recently experienced significant growth with the abundance of data in both scope and volume, and particularly in the Internet of Things (IoT) field. The numerous capabilities of exploiting such data collections through the use of data processing and analysis techniques and the continuous expansion of the application domains they cover has further motivated the ever-evolving IoT landscape.

As a result of the proliferation and diversity of the IoT applications, platforms, software and protocols, the IoT market is highly fragmented and the

complexity of creating services exploiting the multitude of platforms and their connected IoT devices is even more challenging, while interoperability and security aspects are of utmost importance. Indeed, considering the huge number of connected IoT devices and the exponential growth of this market¹ that could be easily observed in Fig. 1, it is imperative to pay attention in the two aforementioned aspects. Therefore, with the emergence of solutions offering interoperability in the diverse IoT environments, covering the first critical aspect in the IoT paradigm, the interactions between IoT platforms, devices and applications involving the exchange of IoT data necessitate the second one, which is to have control over their access as well as the sharing data. Hence, the implementation of mechanisms for data markets that do not only enable the secure exchange of IoT data but also provide the necessary charging, invoicing and billing of transactions becomes essential.

The IoTfeds solution^{2,3} introduces an innovative platform for the secure exchange of IoT data between IoT organizations (platform providers and consumers) developing an open source middleware that implements a fully distributed federation management and marketplace framework. The proposed solution is based on the outcomes of the H2020 symbIoTe project⁴ combined with Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT) such as Blockchain [12]. The symbIoTe software implements an IoT orchestration middleware that supports semantic, syntactic and organizational interoperability enabling IoT platforms federation and collaboration. The incorporation of the Blockchain technology into the IoTfeds ecosystem enables the creation of a decentralized environment bringing several benefits such as: the elimination of the need for a trusted third-party entity [20], novel and efficient business processes [9], transparency,

Fig. 1. IoT market growth.

¹ <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1183457/iot-connected-devices-worldwide/>.

² <http://www.iotfeds.gr/>.

³ <https://github.com/iotfedsproject/>.

⁴ <https://www.symbiote-h2020.eu/>.

and democracy [18], and finally, traceability and enhanced security [10]. However, blockchain integration may also bring some drawbacks that should not be neglected with the most important to be the system performance with respect to the transactions [18]. Associated challenges need to be considered when designing a blockchain solution for a more efficient development.

The IoTfeds platform provides all the necessary mechanisms to IoT organizations to form federations and jointly operate controlled markets for the secure and trusted data exchange and trading. The platform enables the creation of *federated (decentralized)* marketplaces where data services that may consist of data coming from different IoT providers can be built and exposed. It also offers a *global* marketplace where data services from any federated market can be promoted to make them available outside of the federation, including also organizations that do not necessarily belong to any federation. As opposed to related work for data-driven collaboration such as data space and marketplace frameworks [1, 2, 17], IoTfeds enables providers to collaborate and combine their data towards the composition of new data services, encapsulating value sharing and compensation mechanisms.

The decentralized IoT data market is implemented based on the following mechanisms:

- *Decentralized* IoT federation governance using *smart contracts* and voting procedures.
- Semantic *interoperability* within federation and globally.
- Secure and controlled access to IoT data based on *ABAC* mechanisms and *blockchain*.
- Discovery and *distributed search* of IoT data services.
- *Reputation* and *trust* methods.
- *Market mechanisms* with (non-)monetary considerations.

The purpose of this article is the general presentation of the main components composing IoTfeds platform avoiding the technical analysis of each component. The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the main concepts in the IoTfeds ecosystem. Section 3 presents the platform’s architecture with its main architectural subsystems, while Sect. 4 concludes the article.

2 IoTfeds Ecosystem

The IoTfeds platform enables IoT providers to establish federations and jointly provide data services to other IoTfeds members. It can support two types of data services; *single-source data services* offer direct access to data retrieved from a single data source (resource) e.g., an IoT device or data storage medium, and *data products* are bundles of multiple data sources that may come from several providers. Within the IoTfeds ecosystem different federation types may exist.

Fig. 2. IoT Feds value network.

2.1 Value Network

The value network presented in Fig. 2 illustrates the actor roles existing in the federated IoT data markets ecosystems (including IoT Feds) and their business relationships. The IoT Feds platform role positioned at the center of the ecosystem is a role adopted by all the entities contributing to the decentralized realization of IoT Feds platform, which involves the federation interoperability framework *symbIoTe* and its extensions to support the federated markets as well as the *blockchain* network for supporting the decentralized operation of IoT Feds platform and federations formed therein. The IoT data *provider* and *consumer* roles are highly prominent in the IoT Feds ecosystem, being the entities interacting with the IoT Feds platform to form federations and contribute to the formation of collective data services (data provider role) or consume data services (data consumer role).

Each federation is formed by a set of IoT data providers and potentially consumers, however they appear as a separate role in the value network because the IoT Feds platform treats federations as separate *Decentralized Autonomous Organizations* (DAOs) [19], offering the appropriate decentralized mechanisms for their democratized management and governance. An IoT data consumer can also adopt the IoT application provider role utilizing the data obtained by the IoT Feds marketplaces for applications (e.g. a smart parking) offered to end-users (e.g. drivers). Finally, an IoT data provider may own an IoT platform managing data collected from multiple IoT data owners who have ownership of the data coming from IoT devices they maintain.

2.2 Federation Types

Based on its members roles, federations can be categorized to *data providers'* or *mixed federations*. In a data providers' federation *all* federation members *must* contribute IoT data to the federated market, having the role of the IoT data provider. At the same time all members are able to consume IoT data contributed by other federation members, adopting the role of data consumer. In a *mixed federation* the members can adopt either or both roles. The key difference

is that a member does not necessarily have the provider role but may only have the consumer role. Based on the market policies adopted by a federation, the federations can further be categorized to *closed* and *hybrid* federations. In a closed federation the federated data services can be only consumed by the federation members through a *federated marketplace*. In a hybrid federation, the federated data services can be exposed and made available to non-members through the open *global marketplace* of IoTFeds.

2.3 Marketplaces

All data consumers have access to the IoTFeds global marketplace, while access to a federated market is allowed to the members of the respective federation. Products can only be composed within federated marketplaces from data sources (resources) available within its federation. The products created within the federated marketplaces can also be promoted to the global marketplace as prefabricated products. Composing new data services through packaging is not allowed in the global marketplace. Resources and products within federation and marketplaces are discovered and accessed, filtering them based on user's selected criteria (e.g., trust, price etc.) and enforcing appropriate access control policies.

At the market level, the IoTFeds ecosystem has its own currency, named *FedCoin*, through which market transactions are processed, while data access is controlled through the use of access tokens. Markets can be distinguished to product and data source (resource) markets based on their data services type. In markets using the data product concept (product markets) access to data sources is only enabled through the definition of the product, i.e., a data source can itself be a product to be made available for accessing. Making data sources available for accessing directly makes sense only for data source markets, which do not consider the data products concept. In product markets, access to a product's data is controlled through the use of *access tokens* issued by the IoTFeds *Blockchain as a Service* (Baas) subsystem upon the purchase of the product from the respective marketplace (global or federated). In markets where transactions are made at the data source (resource) level, tokens that provide direct access to data sources are managed and traded through the symbIoTe subsystem. In both market types, i.e., the exchange of data sources or products, may be supported offering the potential to data consumers to place their unused access tokens for exchange with other consumers' tokens which provide access to data sources or products they have interest on. Both types of tokens, i.e., resource and product access tokens, are further described in Sect. 3.3.

IoTFeds Example Instance. Figure 3 shows an instance of the IoTFeds ecosystem with three data providers who are also consumers, and two data consumers-only. Providers 1 and 2 form federation 1 (federation of providers), while providers 2 and 3, as well as consumer B form federation 2 (mixed federation). As shown, provider 2 participates in both federations. The providers register all or a subset of their resources to the federated marketplace of each federation they participate. Each of the members of the federation can create

Fig. 3. IoTFFeds ecosystem – with the different markets and interactions.

federated data products by combining any resources available in the marketplace. In Fig. 3, provider 1 creates a product in federated marketplace 1, while consumer B creates a product in federated marketplace 2. The created products can be bought and consumed by their creators or any other federation members. Both federations are open, meaning that the created products are forwarded to the IoTFFeds global marketplace and are available to non-members of the federation. In the aforementioned example, data consumer A can buy products exposed by the federated marketplaces. A different pricing policy can be applied to data products forwarded to the global IoTFFeds marketplace (compared to the federated marketplace) so that prices are more favorable for consumers within the federation. For marketplaces that do not adopt the data product concept, the direct accessing of data sources is performed only through the federated markets.

3 IoTFFeds Architectural Elements

The core subsystems of the IoTFFeds platform that work collaboratively to provide the required functionalities in the IoTFFeds ecosystem include the symbIoTe middleware, the BaaS software and the Marketplace component. The creation, operation and management of the federations as well as their federated marketplaces are supported by the subsystems of symbIoTe and BaaS, with the marketplace acting as the online transactional place that exposes the IoTFFeds market to its users. The symbIoTe software allows IoT platforms to expose selected IoT devices and their data to third-party systems as well as to interact with each other or collaborate to create horizontal solutions through its semantic interoperability approach and a unified and secure interface to access IoT resources. On the other hand, the BaaS subsystem enables the management of user identities and IoT platforms to ensure security and allow tracking of IoTFFeds platform data, integrating distributed mechanisms for pricing each transaction and calculating the trust and reputation levels of data providers and their resources. Through the marketplace, IoT providers can collectively trade IoT data that

Fig. 4. IoTFeds architecture.

may come from several data sources to potential IoT consumers that wish to buy and access them.

As shown in Fig. 4, the decentralized IoT data market is operated by the following architectural parts of the IoTFeds platform: the IoT federation management, access control services (or secure access), distributed search and discovery services, trust and reputation system and the marketplace (or market mechanisms), discussed in the next section. The five architectural parts are provided by integrating the services and functionalities of its core subsystems, i.e., the symbIoTe middleware, the BaaS software and the Marketplace component. Blockchain technologies with the incorporated smart contracts and IoT semantic interoperability with the defined information models comprise the underlying level in the architecture. The IoTFeds services are exposed through high level APIs with an administration panel and a marketplace portal facilitating the management of the IoT federations and their associated marketplaces.

3.1 Democratized IoT Federation Governance

The implementation of the *federation management* mechanism in IoTFeds follows its own DAO approach [3] to achieve decentralized and autonomous federation governance with the creation of a relative smart contract. In the DAO approach any decision is made using voting conducted on the blockchain through a smart contract. Any member in the federation can potentially submit a proposal for consideration by the rest of the members. The request triggers a voting

procedure for the approval or rejection of the proposal. A member can participate in a voting procedure if they own governance tokens. The percentage of the positive votes required to accept a proposal is specified in the *federation rules*. The IoTFeds DAO solution is based on two smart contracts, one related to the federation management and involved rules and actions (elaborated below) and one related to the voting procedure. The rules of an IoTFeds federation define aspects such as: (i) the type of the federation (provider or mixed), (ii) the type of its market (hybrid or closed) and the adopted market mechanisms, (iii) the subscription details (if any), (iv) the supported verticals, (v) the supported ontologies, (vi) governance rules supporting proposals for inviting/removing a member to/from the federation, joining a federation, changing federation rules etc., (vii) voting procedures rules offering a static template to parameterize in each DAO federation, (viii) quality assurance rules specifying the quality metrics to be taken into account, the acceptable quality level and the management mechanisms in case of failure, (ix) the coin to be used (fiat money or FedCoins).

3.2 Interoperability Between the Different Systems

Semantic interoperability in IoTFeds is based on the existing symbIoTe's solution that enables both interoperability by standardization (out-of-the-box) and interoperability by mapping [21]. It relies on symbIoTe's *Core Information Model* (CIM) with Extensions approach [7] with the definition of a basic information model (ontology) that describes the basic entities and their information (vocabulary) that platform providers should use to describe their IoT devices and register them to the system. In symbIoTe, information models have been designed to be generalised and abstract on the one hand but also detailed to enable flexibility to platforms adopting them while covering their needs [8]. The models are inspired by commonly used ontology standards like SSN and SOSA⁵. The approach used also allows platform providers to optionally register their own platform specific information models (PIMs) to the system to include additional device-specific details that cover their own needs. Based on semantic mapping, additional device properties can be interpreted by other platform providers while they can define and store to the system a correlation between their vocabularies (mapping) on how data expressed using one ontology can be translated into the terms of another ontology. A special category of PIM, the Best-practice Information Model (BIM) is also incorporated in the system to cover specific use case domains for out-of-the-box interoperability between the platforms. Within a federation, BIM can be selected to be used or a new PIM that extends CIM can be agreed between the federation members and registered to facilitate data and metadata transactions within it. Within the context of IoTFeds, BIM has been extended to cover Smart City domain needs investigating state-of-the-art ontologies like SAREF4CITY⁶ and NGSILD⁷ for smart city⁸.

⁵ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-ssn/>.

⁶ <https://saref.etsi.org/saref4city/>.

⁷ <https://www.fiware.org/smart-data-models/>.

⁸ http://www.symbiote-h2020.eu/ontology/smartcity_v1.

3.3 Access Control to IoT Data

IoT and blockchain technologies can be combined to control the conditions under which a user can access IoT devices and their data (e.g. when and for how long) creating a verifiable, decentralized and trustworthy environment on the one hand, while enabling the secure and reliable interconnection of a large number of devices on a network on the other hand. In IoTFeds, *Attribute-Based Access Control* (ABAC) mechanisms [14] to achieve secure data access and management at both resource and product levels are used (i.e. for its *access control services*). For instance, only the data provider has the privilege to create a federation and only the members of a federation have access to the federated marketplace.

Resource-Level. In the ABAC methodology, access to resources is controlled through the use of appropriate attributes (properties, roles or permissions associated with a resource in the system) implementing access control policies that make use of them to determine whether an action to a resource is allowed. The access policy defines a specific combination of attributes required to grant access to the IoT resource and is assigned to it by its owner. Therefore, a data consumer can access a resource only if it has a set of attributes that match the provider's predefined access policy.

Product-Level. ABAC mechanisms allow users to search, filter and access IoT resources and products in the participated federation and market according to their permissions. Authorization utilizes symbIoTe's ABAC mechanism combined with a security mechanism implemented at the blockchain network (BaaS subsystem). ABAC mechanism in symbIoTe allows to control user's access to IoT resources (data source level) defining a set of *policies* that cover the required cases, while user actions at product level are controlled by BaaS with the use of access tokens. Each user can be considered to have as a characteristic the specific tokens corresponding to the products in their possession, creating a *wallet* for each user at the *ledger* where their access tokens are stored. When a user successfully purchases a product, the user obtains an access token with the respective parameters (validity period, number of uses, frequency of access etc.). When a user requests access to a product's data, BaaS executes the respective search to the ledger for the user's wallet to locate the token with the name of the product and check its parameters to determine whether user's request can be served (e.g., for a multiple data access product, the remaining uses and if the date is inside the validity period are checked). Access control is done using smart contracts while the user is given the possibility through BaaS to control their wallet and the available tokens by retrieving its content from the ledger.

3.4 Trust and Reputation

In an IoT environment where diverse entities like IoT platforms, devices, services, applications and users interact at a high degree, establishing trust to ensure reliable transactions between trading entities can be a complex task. Reputation and trust systems are valuable tools for assessing the quality of the services

Fig. 5. Trust and reputation system.

provided, when the relevant information is incomplete, asymmetric or “hidden”, while providing incentives to the entities to behave as expected and not to abuse the system. In the IoTfeds platform, the concept of reputation on multiple levels is introduced and leveraged as depicted in Fig. 5 and elaborated below.

- *Data sources.* The reputation score of a data source can facilitate the selection of appropriate quality data sources in product creation at a federated marketplace.
- *Data Products.* A product’s reputation score is determined by the collective reputation score of its constituent data sources. In IoTfeds, the weighted sum aggregation approach [4, 13] is adopted for the calculation. Product reputation scores may be leveraged by consumers for selecting appropriate quality pre-existing products in the federated or global marketplaces of IoTfeds.
- *Data Providers.* A data provider’s reputation score is determined by the collective reputation score of its contributed data sources again utilizing the weighted sum aggregation method. Providers reputation scores are useful for adding/removing a member to/from a federation when its individual reputation score is higher/lower than the minimum reputation score set by the federation. Also, providers with higher reputation scores may have more influence on the decision making of the federation DAO.
- *Federations.* Similarly, the reputation score of a federation is determined by the collective reputation score of all data sources registered to the federation by all federation members utilizing the weighted sum aggregation method. Federation’s reputation can be useful for an organization to select a trusted federation to join.

As described, the reputation scores of data sources are utilized for estimating the reputation scores in all other layers. However, certain inputs are needed to calculate each data source reputation. Two types of inputs are considered in IoTfeds trust and reputation system: (i) the subjective rating of products purchased by the consumers in federated or global marketplaces for a set of

predefined Quality of Experience (QoE) parameters (“Easy of use”, “Value for money”, “Business Enablement”, “Data completeness” etc.) and (ii) the *objective rating* of each data source based on performance measurements obtained from the monitoring system of the platforms on a set of predefined Quality of Service (QoS) parameters (service availability, response time, data precision etc.).

Each federation defines a QoE profile that identifies the set of parameters that are taken into account in product rating and their importance. Accordingly, a QoS profile is defined by the federation including target values for the QoS parameters. Based on the objective and subjective ratings, the IoTfeds Trust and Reputation system calculates and maintains an objective and a subjective score per data source which are combined to periodically update the reputation scores of data sources, products, providers and federations. All calculations (subjective, objective and reputation scores) are performed utilizing the appropriate smart contracts and the scores are maintained on-chain (BaaS subsystem). On the other hand, the data source QoS ratings (monitoring reports) and the product ratings are maintained off-chain (symbIoTe subsystem).

IoTfeds ensures the robustness of its reputation system against malicious users, such as data consumers who aim to damage a competitor’s reputation or providers who report inaccurate performance estimates. Consumer attacks are mitigated by allowing only one objective rating per valid transaction, with an additional fee for each transaction. Provider false reporting is avoided through cross-checking with subjective ratings. Providers who consistently overestimate their performance lose trustworthiness, and their objective reports are excluded from reputation calculations.

3.5 Discovery and Distributed Search of Data Services

As mentioned earlier, data services in IoTfeds can be either *simple IoT resources* from a single IoT provider or more *complex products* (bundles of federated resources) promoted in the federated or global marketplace for purchase. Searching among the available data services is important for end users to select valuable resources or products meeting their needs based on selected criteria, such as location, data type, price and reputation. The symbIoTe platform offers a search mechanism for resources covering criteria like platform id, federation name, resource id, location and observed properties, while considering the filtering policies of the registered resources. Within IoTfeds, searching of resources and products covering criteria related to pricing and reputation is supported by BaaS. Thus, search in IoTfeds is realized on two levels. In the first stage, symbIoTe searches among the entire set of resources within the participated federation for the criteria it supports resulting in a filtered list of resources. At the second level, this list is further filtered and sorted in BaaS based on their price and/or reputation if necessary, while checking their validity. For products discovery, the search service of the marketplace is used supporting various criteria similar to the product’s resources and combined with search in BaaS to additionally filter and sort them based on their price and trust values.

For both procedures, namely the discovery of resources and products, the last step before visualizing the results to the user is the *ranking* procedure [16]. It is indispensable for the proposed ranking algorithm to consider the reputation of resources and products by advertising (ranking higher in the results' list) the highly reputed ones. Thus, there is a close collaboration between trust & reputation system and the data services discovery system. More specifically, the ordering of the results depends on the products' and resources' reputation scores received from the ranking algorithm. However, a randomization factor is also considered in the proposed ranking algorithm to avoid a deterministic approach (i.e. having the same results with the same criteria) and offer a chance for a higher position in the results' list for new products having lower reputation scores. The aforementioned adopted ranking is met in the literature with the term stochastic ranking [6]. The whole procedure of the data services *search and discovery* is depicted in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. IoTFeds Data Services Search.

3.6 IoTFeds Currency and Market Solutions

The IoTFeds ecosystem has its own currency, *FedCoin*, that is based on *ERC-20* fungible tokens [5]. FedCoins are created by the IoTFeds platform and are acquired by the users of the system instead of fiat money (euro, dollars, etc.). All the transactions in the marketplaces are performed in FedCoins. FedCoins are also used for micro-payments, namely transactions related to management aspects within the IoTFeds platform such as the federation governance and marketplace actions, e.g. product creation.

When a provider registers a data source in a federated marketplace, they declare its “value” in terms of FedCoins. This value expresses the cost of including this data source into a product capturing the cost for a single, most recent observation. Accordingly, each product is characterised by a price expressed in FedCoins, which must be paid by a buyer to acquire it. The product’s price is based on the “values” of its constituent data sources and is expressed as a function of the *(i)* number of observations acquired (upon an observation request all data sources in the product are accessed), *(ii)* time window in which the acquired observations can be consumed and *(iii)* frequency of use. Data providers are then compensated according to the “value” and reliability of their data sources contributing to the purchased products.

There are multiple regimes of integrated IoTfeds *market* solutions. Each federated or global marketplace in IoTfeds may focus on different data services (data source or product services), and adopt different service pricing policies (static or dynamic), consumer charging mechanisms (monetary or non-monetary) and provider compensation mechanisms. Next, three applicable in IoTfeds market solutions are highlighted.

Data Product Market. Data products are charged based on their use. Any member of the federation can search for data sources available within it to build the product of interest by paying a product creation fee to the IoTfeds platform. Providers declare the compensation they wish to receive for including the data source in a product as a function of observations number, consumption time-window and frequency of use. These parameters are set by the buyer during the product's purchase. Each provider receives compensation for their contribution to the product depending on the data sources comprising the product and their declared compensation functions. Access to the product is controlled through the use of product access tokens (Sect. 3.3) managed in BaaS that specify the time period of accessing it and the observations frequency and number.

Data Product Exchange. This non-monetary exchange market solution is complementary to the above. In this type of "side" market, the consumers can exchange products they have purchased but have not totally consumed by placing to the exchange market. Each product placed for exchange and its details (expiration date, remaining number of uses, frequency etc.) is visible to all members of the market and any market member can submit a proposal by offering one of its purchased products in return. The concerned consumer is informed for the proposal to accept or reject it. The estimated current products' values can be displayed to the users to facilitate fairness in exchanges. If the offer is accepted the respective access tokens are transferred to their new owners' wallets.

Data Source Exchange. This is an alternative exchange mechanism in the data source level which is suitable for market federated solutions that do not adopt the data product concept and is applied to closed federations. In this solution, bartering takes place without any monetary implications with participants exchanging their respective data sources directly for access to data sources of interest. This approach is based on symbIoTe's *bartering & trading* mechanism where the concept of *Vouchers* [21] is introduced to allow mutual exchange of data. A data provider that wants to access a resource of another IoT platform (data provider) issues a voucher that grants the holder access to one of its resources and offers it to the other party to be consumed at a later date. In an IoTfeds market solution, when a provider requests access to another provider's data sources for a certain number of uses or duration, it offers in return a resource access token managed in symbIoTe promising access to its own platform's data sources for a corresponding number of uses or duration.

3.7 Intuitive Graphical User Interface

The developed platform includes an intuitive graphical user interface (GUI) to control and operate the decentralized market, as shown in the figure below, facilitating user interaction with the IoTFeds ecosystem and its services. The GUI consists of an administration panel and a marketplace portal that enable the management, configuration and operation of the IoTFeds federations and their associated marketplaces respectively. The administration panel is based on the extension and modification of symbIoTe's web-based GUI, providing a control panel for administration and configuration actions regarding the management and parameterization of the system's users, platforms and federations. Within IoTFeds, the administration panel is also accompanied with a marketplace portal operating as an online IoT data marketplace where IoT data providers and/or consumers can trade, buy and exchange IoT data services.

4 Discussion

This article described a decentralized federation management and marketplace framework presenting the architecture of the developed IoTFeds platform. The proposed solution enhances an open source IoT federation interoperability middleware with federated markets and blockchain network to enable the creation of IoT federations and their markets operation supporting the build of data product services from multiple federated resources. The platform follows a micro-services architecture deployed in a containerized environment for improved scalability and performance.

In the current approach data exchanges and interactions within federations are considered supporting the creation of products from data sources of the same federation. Although a data source may be shared in multiple federations participating in the creation of multiple products, each product can only be accessed through its federated market and optionally from the open global data market. Data trading mechanisms between federations and their marketplaces for cross-domain data products towards a cross-domain market operation could be studied. Also, multiple other alternative solutions may appear to IoTFeds based on the preferences of each federation, such as applying more sophisticated market mechanisms for optimal automated creation of products based on consumer requirements or auction for market clearance. Markets for access to data sources based on monthly subscription is another research direction to be investigated.

Finally, the adopted approach of IoTFeds will inspire the CoGNETs⁹ project, as it shares some common principles with the emerging paradigm of Dataspaces [15] such as data sovereignty [11]. Hence, as a future work, the combination of the sophisticated marketplace mechanisms of IoTFeds (such as reputation system, pricing schemes, advanced search etc.) with Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs) and well-established and well-structured Dataspaces reference architectures such as GAIA-X [17] and IDSA [2] for the secure data exchange between entities could be a possible interesting research direction.

⁹ <https://www.cognets.eu/>.

Acknowledgment. This work is partially funded by the IoTFeds project, co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund of the European Union and Greek national funds through the Operational Program Competitiveness, Entrepreneurship and Innovation, under the call RESEARCH - CREATE - INNOVATE (project code: T2EDK-02178) and by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme through the CoGNETs project under Grant Agreement No 101135930.

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